

Mean yield performances of Padmanath. Assam, India, 1985-95.

Year	Location	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)		
		Padmanath	Negheribao	Amonabao
1985	Garumnuria	3.2	2.7	2.8
1986	Garumuria	3.0	-	2.7
	Korson	3.0	2.1	2.7
	Dhalpur	3.3	2.5	3.1
1987	Majuli	3.2	2.3	2.8
	Garumnuria	3.2	2.2	3.0
	Korson	3.1	2.1	2.6
1988	Dhalpur	3.3	2.4	2.9
	Jorhat	3.4	2.0	2.8
	Garumnuria	2.9	2.1	2.3
	Kalabari	3.1	-	-
	Dhalpur	2.5	1.6	1.1
	Dhemaji	3.2	-	-
1989	Dhakuakhana	3.4	-	-
	Jorhat	1.7	1.7	1.9
	Garumuria	3.1	1.8	2.2
	Dhemaji	3.0	-	-
1991	Dhakuakhana	3.2	-	-
	Garumuria	1.1	0.6	-
1992	Korson	3.1	1.4	1.7
	Garumuria	1.3	-	1.1
1994	Mahaijan	1.6	-	1.2
	Garumuria	3.7	-	2.7
1995	Garumuria	1.2	0.9	-
	Dolpota	2.0	1.8	-
	Dhakuakhana	2.1	1.2	-
	Ghilamora	3.0	1.5	-
Pooled av over years and locations		2.7	1.8	2.3

national check Jalamagna with 100% survival, stem elongation score 1, and yield of 2.1 t ha⁻¹, respectively. Padmanath is photoperiod-sensitive and flowers in late October. It is recommended for cultivation in flood-prone lowlands and deeply flooded regions of up to 2 m water in Assam. Padmanath exhibited moderate field tolerance for the major diseases and pests of deepwater rice. Good stem elongation up to 24.8 cm d⁻¹ was also recorded in rising floods. The variety also possesses excellent kneeing ability (38° average for all tillers).

Padmanath has medium-bold awned grains of the dimensions 7.4 × 3.1 mm and a test weight of 26.4 g for 1000 grains. The kernels are white and nonglutinous with a length-breadth ratio of 2.8. It is gaining popularity among the deepwater rice farmers of the state. ■

Panindra: a new deepwater rice for Assam, India

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Besides Padmanath, a new deepwater rice variety, we bred Panindra by the bulk pedigree method after hybridization between Pankaj and Negheribao. Pankaj is an improved high-yielding rice variety adapted to waterlogged situations and Negheribao is a local deepwater rice variety with excellent stem elongation capacity under rising floods up to 3-4 m.

The yield data of Panindra from 1988 to 1995 over 13 locations of the state are presented in the table. Panindra had a mean grain yield of 2.5 t ha⁻¹ over years and locations, exhibiting 33% superiority in yield than the local check variety Amonabao. Panindra was also found superior in grain yield by 50% than its deepwater parent Negheribao. Panindra is tall, elongating with medium slender grains, and suitable to grow in 1-2 m floods in Assam. The variety was also tested in the National Deepwater Rice Yield Trials (PVT6) under the name IET11875 from 1989 to 1993. During 1989, Panindra had a mean yield of 2.0 t ha⁻¹ as compared with the national check variety Jalamagna, which had the mean yield of 2.2 t ha⁻¹ across locations over India in PVT6.

Ranjini (MO 12): a high-yielding rice variety with blast and brown planthopper resistance

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Mean paddy yield of Panindra. Assam, India, 1988-95.

Year	Location	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)		
		Panindra	Negheribao	Amonabao
1988	Garumuria	4.2	2.1	2.3
1990	Korson	4.1	2.9	-
1991	Garumuria	1.7	0.6	-
	Garumuria	1.9	-	1.1
1992	Mohaijan	2.9	-	1.2
	Garumuria	2.3	2.0	1.9
1994	Garumuria	3.1	-	2.7
	Dolpota	3.0	-	2.3
1995	Garumuria	1.1	0.9	-
	Dolpota	1.1	1.8	-
	Dhakuakhana	2.6	1.2	-
	Ghilamora	2.4	1.5	-
	Dhemaji	2.5	2.2	-
Pooled av		2.5	1.7	1.9

During 1990, Panindra had exhibited a mean yield of 2 t ha⁻¹ over India under IVT-DW; during 1992 it ranked second to Ghaghraghat (3.3 t ha⁻¹) and was superior to Jalamagna (1.8 t ha⁻¹).

Panindra is a photoperiod-sensitive variety, flowering by the last week of October in Assam. It is moderately tolerant of major diseases and pests but moderately susceptible to rice stem nematode, *Ditylenchus angustus*. It has outyielded the local deepwater rice varieties of Assam in plant and grain characters. Fair stem elongation rate (21 cm d⁻¹) was also observed for Panindra. Excellent kneeing ability (41°) of the tillers after the flood was also an added advantage to this variety.

Awnless grain of Panindra has a dimension of 7.8 × 2.6 mm with a test weight of 24.3 g for 1000 grains. The nonglutinous white kernel has a length-breadth ratio of 3.0. ■

Rice blast is one of the most serious diseases prevalent in Kuttanadu, the rice bowl of Kerala, a unique deltaic area, 0.5-2.0 m below MSL. Many popular high-yielding varieties of this locality lack blast resistance. A hybridization program was started at RRS, Moncompu, using locally accepted, high-yielding varieties, such as MO 5 and blast-resistant varieties such as